

ESTIMATION OF TIME SINCE INJURY IN MECHANICAL TRAUMA: FORENSIC CHALLENGES AND ADVANCES FROM A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY AT LIAQUAT UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL, HYDERABAD

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Abstract

Background: The ability to estimate Time since Injury (TSI) is a key aspect of forensic medical analysis, particularly in relation to mechanical injury. Estimating the TSI assists in building timelines, corroborating witness testimony and providing supporting information for any court proceedings. The problem is that TSI is difficult to estimate accurately because responses can vary between individuals, there are confounding environmental influences on TSI and clinical judgments are subjective.

Objectives: The aims of this study period were to estimate TSI in reported cases of mechanical trauma at a tertiary hospital where subsequent post injury examination occurred, ascertain how long after injury the medico-legal examination occurred, and assess how compliant clinicians were with the requirements of the Injured Person (Medical Aid) Act 2004, and to provide an account of the forensic difficulties threatening accurate TSI estimation.

Methods: This was a retrospective cross-sectional study of 200 medico-legal cases of mechanical trauma reported (subsequent to post injury examination) to Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad, between June 2023 and July 2024. Data was collected from the medico-legal records and included demographic information, details about the injury, estimations about the time of injury, time of arrival at hospital and time of medico-legal examination. Descriptive and inferential statistical analysis was performed using SPSS (version 26).

Results: Of the 200 cases there were 80 with documentation of "fresh" injuries, with other cases indicating different lengths of time such as "within 2 hours" or "2-3 hours." A mean time from arrival to examination of 224.3 minutes with a very large standard deviation of 20,388.7 minutes indicates very serious errors in documentation. Some cases even presented a negative interval for time. Compliance with the Medical Aid Act 2004 was partial as there were specified delays for administering first aid and in other cases delays initiating a medico-legal documentation.

Conclusion: Estimating TSI in a forensic circumstance is difficult and complex whenever levels of how the accidents are documented variably, because there are no standards to the practice and it is reliant upon what the individual can

observe and document. The reliability and accuracy of TSI would be better enhanced by application of advanced diagnostic tools, digital capabilities for time stamping and reporting formats, alongside a better training of medico-legal practitioners

INTRODUCTION

Estimating Time since Injury (TSI) is a central consideration in forensic medicine. This is particularly true when dealing with incidences involving mechanical trauma, such as assaults, accidents, or abuse [1]. When the age of an injury is more accurately established, this can assist investigators and/or judges in reconstructing a possible sequence of events, authenticate or reject statements made by victims and offenders, and establish approximations of timelines, all of which is especially important in suspects appearing before the court. Similarly, accurate TSI estimation provides support for the legal system in determining culpability and intention of the perpetrator which is also an important consideration in matters of justice [2].

Mechanical injuries (abrasions, contusions, lacerations, incised wounds) appear to demonstrate different patterns of healing depending on the mechanism of force, the kind of weapon used, the anatomical region where the injury occurred, as well as the individual's physiological state [3]. Generally, forensic practitioners have relied on gross morphological changes as well as clinical features (e.g. color of bruising, and degree of scab formation) to approximate time of injury [4]. While these features are an expected learning resource, they remain primarily subjective and may lack reproducibility, due in part to variability in observation, environmental factors (e.g., presence of moisture), pre-existing medical conditions (e.g., fragile skin), and lack of standardised assessment or observational protocols [5].

By virtue of being a developing country, it is especially important for investigators that reliable, scientifically validated estimates of TSI be possible in Pakistan. Unfortunately, these expectations are rarely considered in the peculiar world of the law, where a report may or may not specifically mention such terms as "fresh" or "recent." The study aims to evaluate existing practices of estimating TSI at

Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad, to identify the forensic and procedural challenges faced by medical officers, and to suggest evidence-based measures that enhance the accuracy of reports on medico-legal injuries and improve their consistency. Over the past few decades, several studies have investigated several methods of assessing Time since Injury (TSI) for forensic cases. Some of the above methods produce varying levels of accuracy and reliability. Traditional methods rely heavily on clinical assessments of the characteristics of the wound, specifically looking at swelling, scab development, healing, and changes in color. For instance, Sandhu et al. (2009) noted substantial differences between observers involved in a clinical trial operated in North India that sought to associate wound characterization with age [6]. Ahmad et al. (2015) investigated the predictions of the age of injury in live medicolegal cases in Pakistan, updated during their findings noted them subjectively categorizing and inconsistent documentation often led to wounds being documented as 'fresh' or 'recent' [7]. With recent developments surrounding the research into molecular and histopathological methods, Li et al. (2020) focused on the use of transcriptomics and proteomics methods for forensic pathology [8]. Tomassini et al. (2024), who identified sequence lymphatic and immunohistochemistry and immunofluorescence markers for dating skin lesions within a clinical setting [9]. Despite the recent literature showing positive developments, these techniques are, overall, excluded from numerous traditional medicolegal investigations, primarily as a result of a lack of funding, training, and support in developing countries, further demonstrating the need for continued methods for TSI that are more objective, consistent, and attainable in terms of evidence in a forensic or clinical setting.

Methodology

This study is designed to assess retrospective, cross-sectional data at Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad. Data collection was from June 2023 to July 2024. 200 medico-legal cases with mechanical trauma were included in the study sample. The inclusion criteria included only mechanical injuries, e.g., abrasions, lacerations, contusions, and incised wounds. Any non-mechanical injuries, e.g., burns, poisoning, chemical exposures, and electrocution, were excluded from this study to keep the research specific. The research purpose was to assess how well Time since Injury (TSI) is estimated and record what documentation practices were seen in real-time medico-legal work.

Data were collected from medico-legal case (MLC) records and included details of the patient's age, sex, the nature of the injury sustained, type of weapon used, estimation of TSI, times of arrival at the medico-legal centre and examination, and a brief description of the injury itself. Once data were collected they were entered into Microsoft Excel and analysed using the Statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS, version 26). A set of descriptive statistics (including mean, median, standard deviation and range) were calculated, alongside independent samples t-tests, Mann-Whitney U tests and Pearson's and Spearman's correlation coefficients to evaluate relationships between variables. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences. All patients' data was anonymised, and patient data was secured, with access only to the team of researchers involved in the study, and this was done to ensure confidentiality and compliance with ethical standards.

Results

A total of medical legal cases of mechanical trauma were evaluated in the current study. When classifying

cases by some record of time from occurrence, it was apparent there was significant inconsistency in the recording of this temporal factor. Of the 200 cases included in this analysis, 80 of the cases were simply identified as "fresh", 34 cases were identified as occurring "within 2 hours"; 7 cases were identified as occurring "within 3 hours"; 6 cases were noted as simply "2-3 hours"; and 8 cases were described as having occurred "in the last 4-5 hours". The remaining 65 cases were categorized as having unclear or ambiguous classifications, including general terms like "recent" and "undefined." This variation in terminology across cases suggests considerable irregularity in the medico-legal documentation of the temporality of injury.

The assessment of the time period from patient arrival to the time of medico-legal examination showed large inconsistency, for example, the average time from patient arrival to the time of medico-legal examination was 224.3 minutes, but it had a huge standard deviation of 20,388.7 minutes. The lowest recorded value was -175,680 minutes and the highest was 220,326 minutes. The median was 0 minutes which speaks to the inconsistency with time recording. Overall, these observations imply there could have been clerical/data entry errors that may be inhibiting the reliability of medico-legal reporting. The observations noted only partial compliance with the Injured Person (Medical Aid) Act 2004 as there were repeated instances whereby there were excessive time delays in delivering first aid or executing the medico-legal documentation. There are considerable concerns over compliance with emergency response servicing which relate to the timeliness of service and reliability of service.

The majority of the cases were comprised of individuals aged 20 to 35, as demonstrated in the histogram of the distribution of age, which was right-skewed indicating fewer cases in older age groups (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Histogram showing the age distribution of victims in medico-legal trauma cases\

The common weapon of use among mechanical trauma instances was hard blunt objects, which was the overwhelming bulk of cases used the weapons of hard blunt object, whereas firearms and cutting

weapons made up a minute amount of case instances (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Bar chart illustrating the type of weapons used in mechanical injuries

All 200 medico-legal cases included in this study involved male victims, highlighting a complete male predominance in the sample (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Bar graph showing gender distribution; all cases involved male victims

Discussion

The determination of Time since Injury (TSI) remains a significant difficulty in forensic practice given the subjective nature of clinical descriptions and lack of standardized terminology. In the current study with time intervals described as 'fresh' or vague timeframes like 'within 2 hours', it is essentially impossible to create a consistent timeline. Furthermore, unique biological characteristics among individuals (e.g., age, health status, time to clot, and host immune response) and environmental factors (e.g., temperature) all influence the appearance and healing of wounds, therefore visual assessments become less reliable. All these discrepancies could not only undermine forensic accuracy, but also interfere with the likelihood of legal value of medico-legal assessments if the assessments were produced in a court context.

The average delay of more than 224 minutes between hospital arrival and medico-legal examination in this study indicates operational delinquencies and the failure to accurately document the timing of injury, where some entries had even been recorded with negative time intervals owing to clerical errors. Further consideration is given to delayed reporting by victims, often attributable to fear, ignorance, and barriers to access, which only serves to complicate the accurate estimation of TSI. While sophisticated approaches (for example, artefactual methods using MRI, CT scans, or histological staining) offer a tendency for improved accuracy, such methods are rarely applied in every day medico-legal applications, particularly in locations where resources are scarce. This reinforces the critical need for standardized documentation of injury (to include time and manner), more professional development of Medico-Legal Officers (MLOs) and the phased assimilation of new forensic technology to improve the objectivity and consistency of injury age estimation.

Conclusion

The study illuminates the independent difficulties in the development of an estimate of Time since Injury (TSI) in mechanical trauma cases in standard medico-legal practice. General use of unspecific and inconsistent terminology support by erroneous data entry and time delays in practice, cast doubt over the

reliability of medico-legal documentation. These aspects generate consequences that may cause failure of justice in court, as it becomes complicated proving the timing of injuries. In order to facilitate more accurate TSI estimates, we recommend that new standards are developed for documenting information, that there is ongoing training provided to medico-legal practitioners, and that alternative modern forensic modalities including modern imaging and histopathological analysis are used. These recommendations would have a huge impact upon the scientific utility of any medico-legal reports that could be used to allow for the possibility of more accurate, timely, and just outcomes in court proceedings.

References

- RAMSON, D., TRAUMA, FORENSICS, AND THE LAW: THE LAST CUT IS THE DEEPEST. *ANZ J. Surg*, 2023. **93**(S1): p. 234-242.
- Roberts, J.M., et al., The utility of the Trauma Symptom Inventory as a primary and secondary assessment instrument for forensic practice in legal settings. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 2022. **104**(2): p. 221-233.
- Patra, A.P., S. Subramanyam, and J. Janardhanan, *Medicolegal Aspects of Mechanical Wounds*, in *Medical Jurisprudence & Clinical Forensic Medicine*. 2023, CRC Press. p. 102-119.
- Ranson, D.L. and N. Firth, *Forensic pathology. Forensic Odontology: Principles and Practice*, 2016: p. 134-166.
- Burch, J., et al., Keep it simple: peristomal skin health, quality of life and wellbeing. *British Journal of Nursing*, 2021. **30**(Sup6): p. 5-24.
- Sandhu, S., et al., Age estimation of injury from abrasion-a clinical study from north India. 2009.

- Saleem, I.A.N.S.M. Estimation of Time Since Injuries (Age of Wound) in Living Medico-Legal Cases of Mansehra. in Medical Forum Monthly. 2015.
- Li, N., et al., Vitality and wound-age estimation in forensic pathology: review and future prospects. Forensic sciences research, 2020. 5(1): p. 15-24.
- Tomassini, L., et al., Dating skin lesions of forensic interest by immunohistochemistry and immunofluorescence techniques: a scoping literature review. Diagnostics, 2024. 14(2): p. 168.

